

Illuminating the Diversity-Fitness Trade-Off in Black-Box Optimization

Maria Laura Santoni¹[0009-0007-7389-2555], Elena Raponi²[0000-0001-6841-7409],
Aneta Neumann³[0000-0002-0036-4782], Frank Neumann³[0000-0002-2721-3618],
Mike Preuss²[0000-0003-4681-1346], and Carola Doerr^{1,4}[0000-0002-4981-3227]

¹ Sorbonne Université, LIP6, Paris, France

² LIACS, Leiden, The Netherlands

³ The University of Adelaide, Adelaide, Australia

⁴ CNRS, Paris, France

Abstract. This documents supplements PPSN 2024 submission “Illuminating the Diversity-Fitness Trade-Off in Black-Box Optimization” and provides additional figures not shown in the main part for reasons of space:

- Results for $D = 5$
- Results for $k = 10$ and $D \in \{2, 5, 10\}$

Fig. 1: $D = 5$. Trade-off between average loss and minimum distance for an optimal batch of $k = 5$ points. 10 independent runs of the greedy approach starting from different point portfolios of size $T = 10\,000$.

Fig. 2: Same as Figure 1, but for initial portfolio size $T = 1000$.

Fig. 3: $D = 2$. Trade-off between average loss and minimum distance for an optimal batch of $k = 10$ points. 10 independent runs of the greedy approach starting from different point portfolios of size $T = 10000$.

Fig. 4: Same as Figure 3, but for initial portfolio size $T = 1000$.

Fig. 5: $D = 5$. Trade-off between average loss and minimum distance for an optimal batch of $k = 10$ points. 10 independent runs of the greedy approach starting from different point portfolios of size $T = 10000$.

Fig. 6: Same as Figure 5, but for initial portfolio size $T = 1000$.

Fig. 7: $D = 10$. Trade-off between average loss and minimum distance for an optimal batch of $k = 10$ points. 10 independent runs of the greedy approach starting from different point portfolios of size $T = 10000$.

Fig. 8: Same as Figure 7, but for initial portfolio size $T = 1000$.